

USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN PRESCHOOL ORGANIZATIONS

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida darslarda innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanishda o'quvchilarni faollashtirish usullari muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Maktabgacha ta'lim, innovatsion texnologiya, metod, dars, o'qitish usuli, interfaol ta'lim.

Annotation: This article discusses the methods used to activate students in the use of innovative technologies in the classroom in preschool education.

Key words: Preschool education, innovative technology, method, lesson, teaching method, interactive education.

Abstract: This article discusses ways to activate students in the use of innovative technologies in lessons in preschool educational institutions.

Key words: Pre-school education, innovative technology, method, lesson, teaching method, interactive education.

In order to organize the educational process using innovative methods, first of all, it is necessary to develop a clear lesson plan and project. When designing a lesson, the teacher should clearly define the forms of their work and the scope of students' work in the process of acquiring skills. It is also important to know what teaching methods to use. A teaching method is a sequence of actions to achieve a goal, or a specific goal that has been developed. Interactive learning is a system of methods based on constant communication, reading together and active participation. It's about interaction, it's about collaborative learning. The great philosopher Confucius said 2,500 years ago:

—I forget what I heard, I remember what I saw, I understand when I do it independently. We use a lot of interactive methods and exercises in the classroom to work with students, in pairs and in groups.

—Presentation in explaining a new topic from —Small lecture, —Role play, —Mental attack, —The wheel methods and —Everyone, teaches everyone, —Fruit salad, —Impulse —Life way, —Situations —Mind wheel —Chocolate rain exercises. In this process, students work in groups, collaborate, perform independently and remember in the learning process. First of all, students develop friendly agreement and life skills. —Friendly agreement - discipline, activism, mutual respect, rule of mind, creativity, creative fine, regulation (clear, concise, concise statement)

—Life skills - ability to communicate, creative thinking, coping with stress, emotional control, problem solving, self-analysis, decision making, critical thinking. The “small group work” method can also be used to divide students into groups. The “energizer” exercise can be used to divide students into groups. In this case, 3-4 pictures of different fruits are placed on the table in reverse. Students take turns taking these pictures. The students with the picture of grapes are in one group, the children with the picture of tomatoes are in the second group, and the children with the picture of apples are in the third group. Each team goes and sits in its own place. These groups can be used in a variety of ways to resolve contentious issues, engage in discussions, or summarize lessons after a section has been studied based on the curriculum. All of these methods involve collaboration between teacher and student, active participation of the student in the learning process. Here are some of them: The “wheel” method can be used to reinforce the topic of “word groups” in native language lessons. You can divide students into groups using any method. This method allows students to work in pairs, one relationship is formed. This exercise involves groups of two or three students. The first student says one of the terms related to the topic, the second student repeats the term the first student said, and he

or she says the same term. The third student repeats the previous two terms and adds one term. It's the first student's turn. Any student who gets lost or repeats the term will be eliminated from the game. In organizing this game, the goal should be clear and focus on what knowledge, skills and abilities the students will acquire. For example: Say the words related to the word group —Otl: Education is a process of increasing the effectiveness of lessons, strengthening students' knowledge, using innovative technologies and interactive methods to increase students' interest in the lesson. it is advisable to use a variety of visual aids. Handmade and creative exhibitions are especially important. For example, one of these exhibitions is a poster with a picture of a simple tree branch, on which you can place flowers, birds and fruits. This handmade exhibition can be used in all disciplines. Through this exhibition, students learn about the interdependence of sciences, the sanctity of the homeland, the love of nature, the care of animals. The following is an example of an exhibition: For example, when we use flowers in math class, we can continue the exercise. On one side of the flowers are written math questions, and on the other side are the links. Students read the math questions written on one side of the flowers and attach the articulated side to a tree branch. —Whoever answers the questions correctly will help the tree to bloom. — says the teacher. In this way, the flowers on the branches of the tree form syllables. Thus, the use of various interactive methods in the classroom is very effective in increasing the effectiveness of lessons, enriching the level of knowledge of students. Stimulates students' interest in knowledge. Students try to prepare well for the lesson. Such methods increase the fun and impact of the lesson, making students active participants in the learning process. We can use a variety of interactive methods and exercises to help students do and understand independently.

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